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The Distribution of Irrigated Agricultural Land at World Level

Between 2010 and 2020 it grew by an average of 4.8%

The World Bank calculates the percentage of irrigated agricultural land as a percentage of total agricultural land. Irrigated agricultural land refers to agricultural areas specially supplied with water, including lands irrigated by controlled flooding. The dataset has many missing values and therefore for many countries the historical series is missing.

Ranking of countries by value of irrigated agricultural land in 2020. Bangladesh ranks first in value of irrigated agricultural land with value accounting for 82.08%, Suriname with 71.43% and Pakistan with 52.66%. In the middle of the table are Denmark with 9.01%, Jordan with 8.10% and Oman with 7.40%. The ranking is closed by Belarus with 0.37%, Mongolia with 0.05% and Iceland.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change in irrigated agricultural land between 2010 and 2020. Romania ranks first in the value of the percentage change in irrigated agricultural land between 2010 and 2020 with a value of 491.43%, followed by from Serbia with 109.04%, and from the Slovak Republic with 63.29%. In the middle of the table are Azerbaijan with a value of 3.97%, followed by Armenia with 3.65% and Turkey with 3.31%. The ranking is closed by Australia with -12.6%, followed by Jordan with -15.81% and Mauritius with -16.41%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The analysis highlights the presence of two clusters made up as follows:

- Cluster 1: Serbia, Slovakia, Romania, Ukraine, Czech Republic, Australia, Afghanistan, Slovenia, Belarus, Armenia, Jordan, Kyrgyzstan, Spain, Turkey, Ecuador, Albania, United Arab Emirates, Mauritius;
- Cluster 2: Pakistan, India, Suriname, Malta; Azerbaijan.

By calculating the median of the clusters for each element, it is possible to identify the following ordering of the clusters, i.e. $C2=39.96 > C1=7.3$.

Machine learning and predictions. A machine learning analysis for predicting the future value of the percentage of irrigated agricultural land is presented below. The algorithms are analyzed according to their ability to maximize the R-squared and to minimize the MAE, MSE and RMSE. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the data while the remaining 20% of the data were used for the actual prediction. A ranking is created for each indicator. Rankings are added up. The algorithm that

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has the lowest ranking is considered the “Best Predictor” algorithm. The following ordering of the clusters is therefore identified, i.e.:

- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff equal to 5;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff of 7;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff of 12;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 16;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 20;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value equal to 24;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value equal to 28;
- Linear Regression with a value of 32.

Therefore by applying the best predictor algorithm or the ANN it is possible to predict the future trend of the analyzed variable for the following countries:

- Armenia with a growth of +5.97%;
- Czech Republic with +245.27%;
- Spain with +1.09%;
- Kyrgyz Republic with +5.48%;
- Mauritius with +11.70%;
- Suriname with -18.92%;
- Slovenia with +195.69%.

The application of the best predictor algorithm highlights a substantially increasing trend in the value of the percentage of irrigated agricultural land in the countries analyzed.

Network analysis using the Euclidean distance. A network analysis using the Euclidean distance is presented below. In particular, two network structures are identified, one of which is simplified and one is complex.

Particularly:

- Slovakia and Ukraine are connected in a relationship having value equal to 0.033.

There is a complex network structure as given below namely:

- Australia has a connection with Slovenia worth 0.23, with the Czech Republic worth 0.021, and with Belarus worth 0.029;
- Slovenia has a connection with Australia worth 0.023, with the Czech Republic worth 0.021, and with Belarus worth 0.012;
- Belarus has a connection with Australia for a value of 0.029 units, with Slovenia for a value of 0.021 units with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.033;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Slovenia with a value of 0.021, with Australia with a value of 0.012, and with Belarus with a value of 0.033.

Obviously the presence of network relationships does not indicate the presence of a cause-effect relationship. Indeed, network analysis does not imply causality. Rather, it is a question of highlighting relationships in the data structure of countries that tend to have similar trends at the metric level.

Conclusions. The percentage of irrigated agricultural land grew by an average of 4.48% between 2010 and 2020 in the countries analyzed. The World Bank dataset has many missing data. There are many countries absent from the World Bank dataset. It follows that the result is certainly partial and cannot be generalized beyond the countries explicitly analyzed. The analysis shows that it is the countries of

South Asia that have the greatest presence of irrigated land. This analysis is compatible with the GDP structure of India, where the agricultural component is still relevant due to the still reduced industrialization and servitization. The predictive analysis highlights a further growth of irrigated agricultural land in the countries analyzed. This growth may be due to the ability of the countries considered to develop real competitive advantages in agriculture by acquiring a specific role in the dynamics of international trade. In any case, it is possible that bio-technological changes induced by scientific research in agriculture could induce modifications in the current structure of agricultural markets worldwide.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Country	2020	Prediction	%
Armenia	0,125328503	0,132809613	5,97
Czechia	0,003636446	0,012555398	245,27
Spain	0,197212304	0,199364121	1,09
Kyrgyz Republic	0,131163437	0,138355971	5,48
Mauritius	0,253384713	0,283020087	11,70
Suriname	1	0,81079808	-18,92
Slovenia	0,003979043	0,011765767	195,69

	ANN	PNN	Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	Random Forest Regression
R^2	0,984307603	0,928254632	0,28035618	0,879069415
mean absolute error	0,027205605	0,057296753	0,184312761	0,065144277
mean squared error	0,00161686	0,008133358	0,074731655	0,013603689
root mean squared error	0,040210203	0,090185132	0,273370911	0,116634852
	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression	Simple Regression Tree
R^2	0,969328693	-0,84571723	-0,597542354	-0,111625539

<i>mean absolute error</i>	0,029557378	0,31569782	0,24357907	0,213491137
<i>mean squared error</i>	0,004596427	0,217511967	0,158622074	0,101893672
<i>root mean squared error</i>	0,067796951	0,466381782	0,398273868	0,319207882

	R²	MAE	MSE	RMSE	SUM
<i>ANN</i>	1	2	1	1	5
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	2	1	2	2	7
<i>PNN</i>	3	3	3	3	12
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	4	4	4	4	16
<i>Gradient Boosted Trees Regression</i>	5	5	5	5	20
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	6	6	6	6	24
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	7	7	7	7	28
<i>Linear Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32

Rank	Country	2020	Rank	Country	2020
1	Bangladesh	82,08	25	Jordan	8,10
2	Suriname	71,43	26	Oman	7,40
3	Pakistan	52,66	27	Afghanistan	6,50
4	India	39,96	28	Mexico	6,24
5	Malta	33,72	29	Malaysia	5,16
6	Israel	33,40	30	Romania	3,48
7	Azerbaijan	30,65	31	Germany	3,05
8	United Arab Emirates	23,04	32	El Salvador	2,29
9	Lao PDR	21,73	33	Sudan	2,26
10	Cyprus	20,01	34	Panama	1,88
11	Ecuador	18,45	35	Serbia	1,48
12	Mauritius	18,37	36	Slovak Republic	1,24
13	Qatar	17,57	37	Croatia	1,14
14	Iran, Islamic Rep.	16,96	38	Ukraine	1,05
15	Albania	15,61	39	Kazakhstan	0,85
16	Uzbekistan	14,53	40	Slovenia	0,65
17	Spain	14,38	41	Czechia	0,62
18	Turkiye	13,81	42	Niger	0,57
19	Myanmar	13,18	43	Ethiopia	0,47
20	Tajikistan	11,57	44	Australia	0,43
21	Kyrgyz Republic	9,69	45	Belarus	0,37
22	Moldova	9,52	46	Mongolia	0,05
23	Armenia	9,27	47	Iceland	0,00
24	Denmark	9,01			